

ISic4234

I.Sicily inscription 4234

Language

Ancient Greek

Type**Material**

volcanic (pietra di Monte Rosa)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Sporadic find of 1950 in the excavation of trench IX (prop. Cincotta-Giuffre, via Diana)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 1004

Physical Description

Fragmentary stele

Dimensions

Height 46 cm

Width 35.5 cm

Depth 13.5 cm

Layout

Text over two lines

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 50 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Κλωδίας
2. Ἀριστοβούλας

Apparatus

Text of I.Lipara

Translation (en)

(tomb) of Klodia Aristoboula

Commentary

I.Lipara observes that the inscription pertains to the re-use of the stele, which was probably originally anepigraphic.

Digital identifiers:

PHI 334801

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 695

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